

Call for Proposals: International Data Space (IDS) Technical Development and Pilot for Scholarly Communication Usage Data Exchange

Prepared by the OA Book Usage Data Trust (OAEBUDT) effort

Pilot Project Summary

A global network of scholarly book stakeholders aim to launch a certifiable [International Data Space](#) (IDS) to support cross-platform data exchange, rights-based access and transaction auditing related to the sharing and aggregation of web analytics. Specifically, the [OA Book Usage Data Trust \(OAEBUDT\)](#) effort wants to pilot a scholarly impact related IDS with the focused use case of exchanging standardized book and chapter item related page view and download web analytics across commercial, public, and nonprofit publishers, platforms and services. This project complements ongoing, separate IDS “governance building block” work by documenting and establishing a core sandbox and production OAEBUDT IDS architecture with user input, and piloting data exchange via the OAEBUDT IDS with an “alpha” cohort of six data providers and/or data recipients. While this project will pilot the IDS data connectors and exchange across data providers and data recipients in Europe and North America, the developed IDS test and production environments must be developed to support multilingual user interfaces as the IDS will support global usage data exchange for the humanities and social sciences.

This Scope of Work (SOW) includes nine project deliverables for a minimum viable OAEBUDT-IDS technical pilot. These include:

1. **OAEBUDT International Data Space (OAEBUDT-IDS) Architecture Diagram:** an image that illustrates both the cloud based systems and processes that operate the OAEBUDT-IDS and how data flows between OAEBU data creators and recipients through the IDS system. This deliverable will be provided in both an editable raw design file and high resolution graphic (e.g. .png) so that the project can update the image independently over time.
2. **Three slide decks and/or recorded <10 minute presentations** over the life of the project to provide project updates and solicit feedback from the OAEBUDT Technical Advisory Committee (TAC). These materials should support the confirmation of direction and receiving of guidance on the OAEBUDT-IDS technical development. Presentations are expected at scheduled TAC meetings when there are substantial updates. During the second half of 2024, the TAC will meet from 13:00-14:00 UTC on: July 11th, September 12th, and November 21st.
3. **Secure, open source minimum viable sandbox OAEBUDT-IDS environment** to support iterative development and pilot partner access and testing through June 2025 that has the following features:
 - o the ability to isolate, ensure, and audit limited OAEBU data visibility, exchange, and access among specified parties, without accidental disclosure or data visibility to others
 - o compliance with European regulations for data intermediation, governance, data privacy, and data marketplaces for a [data intermediation service](#), including at a minimum the [Data Governance Act \(DGA\)](#) ([explanation](#)), the [Digital Markets Act \(DMA\)](#), [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\)](#) and other applicable regulations given the geolocation of participating pilot partners
 - o compliance with existing and/or emerging IDSA standards and protocols for data space components so that the resulting IDS and its components are eligible to be certified in support of the OAEBUDT-IDS serving as a neutral data intermediary, including those in the IDS-RAM
 - o a demonstration account through June 2025 within the sandbox OAEBUDT-IDS environment that illustrates the **data recipient** user experience and can be shared publicly
 - o a demonstration account through June 2025 within the sandbox OAEBUDT-IDS environment that illustrates the **data provider** user experience and can be shared publicly.
 - o a test account that can be repeatedly provisioned to potential data recipients/data providers in isolation to allow them to test IDS connectors without exposing their data to other IDS users

4. **Production open source minimum viable OAEBUDT-IDS environment** that meets IDS certification requirements and supports OAEBU data exchange across four to six pilot partner data providers and/or data recipients through June 2025
 - the ability to isolate, ensure, and audit limited data visibility, exchange, and access among specified parties, without accidental disclosure or data visibility to others
 - compliance with European regulations for data governance, data privacy, and data marketplaces
 - compliance with existing and/or emerging IDSA standards for data space components
 - compliance with the OAEBUDT Rulebook
 - a production account through June 2025 for each pilot partner data provider or data recipient, including organizations that act in both capacities.
5. An **OAEBUDT-IDS Data Inventory** describing the nature and attributes of data elements being exchanged via the OAEBUDT-IDS pilot among the six pilot participants.
6. **Issue list of the open and closed development issues** identified during discovery and development, with resolution status and/or blocking issues; The information can be provided for further maintenance and updates via an open source service (e.g. Github, GitLab) or other structured format that can be openly published (spreadsheet, etc.). Note: including the issue list with the open source codebase is preferred.
7. A **suggested OAEBUDT-IDS technical roadmap** (Kanban diagram) proposing additional phased OAEBUDT-IDS research and development based on lessons learned and feedback received during the IDS pilot period.
8. **Minimum viable documentation and/or training/materials** to support IDS administration transition to OAEBUDT staff; adaptation and/or reference to existing open documentation is encouraged to reduce overall project costs as much as possible.
9. **OAEBUDT-IDS architecture cost information** for ongoing expenses clarifying: a) the minimum annual licensing and staffing costs associated with maintaining the OAEBUDT IDS sandbox, and b) the minimum cost per additional user to onboard additional data providers or recipients to the production OAEBUDT-IDS. This information can be provided in a spreadsheet or document form.

To support transparency, openness, and further development, all deliverables must be provided without restriction for open publishing and distribution. Consultants may propose providing open documentation in open platforms (e.g. ReadtheDocs, GitHub, etc.); OAEBUDT staff will also publish versions of all documentation and images openly with attribution in Zenodo under a CC-BY license.

Note: The OA Book Usage Data Trust is actively fundraising for this work. The proposal selected for this work will be made publicly accessible to support fundraising and awareness raising efforts.

Anticipated Timeline

Proposals will be reviewed as they are received. Partner selection is anticipated by May 31, 2024 but may occur earlier. Once funding is secured, we hope work could begin within two months of notification. Including opportunities for OAEBUDT Technical Advisory Committee input, we ask that a project timeline be proposed for a four to six month period for the scope of work below. If consultants feel this timeline is problematic, proposals are welcome to note any concerns and propose an alternative timeline.

About the OA Book Usage Data Trust

Since 2015, an international, multi-stakeholder research effort has grown through projects to facilitate the direct sovereign data exchange and benchmarking of open and proprietary usage data about Open Access books. With support from the Mellon Foundation, stakeholders from across five continents have collaborated to document book metadata and impact reporting challenges, their book usage data supply chain, applications,

and related data governance frameworks. A community-based Board of Trustees guides this OA Book Usage Data Trust (OAEBU-DT) scholarly infrastructure effort as it aims to achieve the vision of “*Community Governed Sharing of Quality, Interoperable, Open Access (OA) Book Usage Data*” by “*exchanging reliable usage data in a trusted, equitable, and community-governed way.*”

OA Book Usage Data Supply Chain and Problem Identification

From [2018-2019](#), global book stakeholders gathered to explore the challenges related to the reporting and analysis of global multi-channel, multi-platform digital book access and use.¹ To implement the resulting recommendations, the Mellon Foundation awarded a [2020-2022 project](#) led by the Book Industry Study Group trade association and researchers at the University of North Texas, Educopia Institute, University of Michigan, and Curtin University. This team prototyped a repository-based centralized solution to aggregate multi-platform data and present it via Kibana dashboards. This effort attempted to address the challenges faced by public and commercial digital book stakeholders who aimed to exchange, aggregate and benchmark web analytics for digital book objects that are currently provided by suppliers through a diverse range of APIs, reports, dashboards, spreadsheets, and emails. [OA eBook Usage Data Analytics and Reporting Use Cases by Stakeholder](#) were documented, ultimately informing development of a proof of concept dashboard, which was further developed and launched as a [Book Analytics Dashboarding service](#) at the OAPEN Foundation². As [summarized by the technical team](#), open source technical documentation and research from this ingest>repository>dashboard solution to the multi-platform data aggregation and benchmarking challenge included:

- an [OA Books Supply Chain Mapping Report](#), including [OA eBook Supply Chain Maps for Distribution and Usage Reporting](#)
- A [data inventory](#) of related OAEBU data from a sample set of data providers
- a [GitHub repository of Apache Airflow workflow automation code to fetch, process, and analyze usage data](#) for the dashboard pilot from key sources including DOAB, Google Analytics, Google Books, IRUS-UK, OAPEN, and ONIX; updates include [schemas and workflow documentation](#)
- [Technical documentation on the ingest, processing, and output of OA Book Usage \(OAEBU\) “telescope” connectors](#)³
- [Technical documentation on OAEBU data processing workflows for mapping book products, linking metrics, and exporting results](#)

Shift to an International Data Space (IDS)

Due to the passage of the EU Data Governance Act, the OAEBUDT research team split off the ingest>repository>dashboard effort recognizing that a data space must neutrally support the many such public and private data analytics services in this industry as a neutral data intermediation service. The [OA Book Usage Data Trust](#) effort separated and intentionally moved away from a repository solution towards an IDS model with data sovereignty supported through controlled data connectors. The resulting OAEBUDT team focused on adapting and launching a certifiable data space following IDS standards to provide a controlled data exchange environment for organizations that must treat usage and impact data as sensitive, controlled information due to ethical, privacy, or programmatic concerns or legal compliance.

IDS Governance Building Block Development

In 2022, the Mellon Foundation awarded funds to a project team led by The University of North Texas, OpenAIRE, and OPERAS to develop IDS “governance building blocks” for the OA Book Usage Data Trust in line with the *Design Principles for International Data Spaces (IDS)*⁴ and emerging specifications for data space certification. To date, this project has produced a draft rulebook for data space participation, governance, and is drafting its sustainability model in preparation for a 2025 operational launch.

¹ Brian O’Leary, & Kevin Hawkins. (2019). Exploring Open Access Ebook Usage. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.17613/8rty-5628>

² Note: This pilot dashboard was decommissioned and replaced by a newer version available at: uomp.book-analytics.org

³ Note: Documentation is now hosted at: documentation.book-analytics.org

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5244996>

IDS Technical Building Block Work to Date

Existing Scholarly Infrastructures Fit to IDS Role Gap Analysis & Recommendations

The OAEBUDT team prioritizes open source and partnering with existing infrastructures as is feasible to reduce overall burdens to the scholarly communications ecosystem. To inform the technical development of the OAEBUDT-IDS, a consulting firm (67 Bricks) was retained to explore if existing open scholarly or research infrastructures were capable of providing core defined IDS services to the OAEBU-DT. Existing infrastructures were identified, surveyed, and interviewed to see if they could provide the: a) **IDS Meta Data Broker Service**, i.e. index service of metadata shared by data connectors to facilitate discover data specific to the OA Book Publishing and Discovery⁵, b) **IDS Clearing House** for logging of data exchange, transformation, and clearing functions⁶, c) **IDS App Store Provider** to provision dataspace apps that transform, aggregate, or otherwise analyzes the transited data, d) **IDS Vocabulary Providers** to manage ontologies, metadata, and persistent identifiers related to OAEBU data, including industry standard persistent identifier authorities: ORCID, ROR, ONIX, ISBN, and e) **IDS Identity Provider**⁷ Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS) capable of asserting user and organizational identities with associated security and trust levels. In their [report](#), consultants concluded that due to a lack of ISO/IEC 27000 series compliance and low awareness of emerging IDS specifications, none of the researched scholarly infrastructures were well aligned to play a core IDS role for the OAEBUDT at this time.⁸ Hence, this SOW follows the recommendation of adapting and adopting open source IDS services already in use in other industrial domains for the technical OAEBUDT-IDS pilot.

Technical Advisory Committee

As a part of the Governance Building Block project, community governance mechanisms have been established for the OAEBUDT effort, including an elected [Board of Trustees](#) and affiliated [board committees](#) to inform various aspects of OAEBUDT development and operations. In January 2024, the board-level Technical Advisory Committee (TAC) was launched to inform the technical development and implementation roadmap for the OAEBUDT-IDS as it adapts the IDS-RAM standards for sensitive scholarly communications usage and impact data exchange. This global group of 16 experts in scholarly infrastructure, usage data standards, aggregation, and reporting; and identity and authentication management meets every other month or as needed. The TAC will act as an advisory body for this project, providing feedback and input on direction. Decisions may be escalated to the Board of Trustees, depending on a decision's impact on other aspects of OAEBUDT-IDS operations (cost, staffing, etc.).

Technical pilot partner recruitment: alpha/beta cohorts

Partners are now ready to develop and pilot a minimum viable OA book usage data focused IDS technical infrastructure. The Executive Director and Community Manager of the OAEBUDT have been identifying committed pilot partners for both a first "alpha" and second "beta" cohort. Continuing conversations have been supplemented with [documentation](#), and four organizations are now committed to participate as data providers / data recipients in the first cohort supported through this SOW.

Note: Each of the two cohorts of organizations using the OAEUBDT-IDS will be independently studied to understand the impacts of OAEBUDT-IDS participation. The "alpha" cohort of the first four -six pilot partners (working with the team selected through this proposal) will be automatically enrolled in this "Return on Investment" study. The second "beta" cohort will onboard after the completion of this SOW to test and allow refinement of the OAEBUDT-IDS prior to the planned public OAEUBDT-IDS service launch slated for 2025. The nine deliverables from this SOW will be further refined along with onboarding processes with the "beta cohort" through June 2025.

⁵ Bader, Sebastian. (2020). Specification: IDS Meta Data Broker (1.0). Pgs 11-12. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5675076>

⁶ Bastiaansen, Dr. ir. Harrie, Bramm, Georg, Ceballos, Juan, Gall, Mark, & Kolenstart, Maarten. (2020). Specification: IDS Clearing House (1.0). Pgs 7-8. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5675765>

⁷ <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/idsa/blob/main/how-to-build-data-spaces/3-Build-Components.md#identity-management>

⁸ Brown, R., Howat, A., & Schivas, J. (2024). IDS Technical Gap Analysis | Assessing the readiness of open scholarly infrastructures for an International Data Space role. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10790782>

Proposal notes

Proposals should describe any incremental costs related to adding pilot organizations after the initial “alpha” cohort pilot. Proposals should also note the procedure and costs associated with adding users during and after this project to the production IDS environment, recognizing that a second cohort and a scalable service launch are expected within twelve months.

The sandbox and production IDS created through this project should be able to be continued beyond the life of the project. Any platform lock-in should be noted in the proposal. The proposal should also explain anticipated per user IDS costs that should be budgeted for to add production IDS users after the completion of this project. Finally, the proposal should note whether the proposing firm is available to assist with future IDS onboarding beyond the life of this project, and at what cost, or how the IDS environments would continue to be supported without the proposing firm involved..

Budget notes

To support sustainability planning, we ask that proposals address the following questions:

- 1) How does the approach reduce long-term administration, maintenance, and participation costs while providing an open-source IDS infrastructure for both
 - a) the OAEUBDT-IDS Coordinating Office administering the IDS and
 - b) organizational OAEUBDT IDS data providers and/or data recipients connecting to the IDS?
- 2) What technical staff (role and time commitment) is expected to be required to collaborate with the proposed team both at time of pilot onboarding and on an ongoing annual basis at:
 - a) the OAEUBDT Coordinating Body,
 - b) each Data Provider, and
 - c) each Data Recipient?
- 3) What would be the incremental cost to add accounts and configure additional data provider/recipient data connectors for the IDS? While the above Scope of Work aims to connect and test the IDS for 4 to 6 organizations, we have some that may want to join before June 2025 and want to understand what that would require in terms of cost and time..
- 4) How will you leverage past research conducted, including data supply chain, data inventories, and technical documentation? Note, members of the Curtin University research team are available to engage in knowledge transfer at a rate of AUD\$168 per hour. A separate research services agreement would need to be executed between the proposer and Kathryn Napier via Curtin University.

Broader impacts

Once operational, the OA Book Usage Data Trust will provide a cyberinfrastructure network in line with European Data Governance regulations, certified according to forthcoming European Industry Data Space trust and security standards to support global ebook usage data exchange among libraries, publishers, repositories, and the many platforms and services that wish to innovate with such metrics through data analytics and visualization services. By leveraging existing IDS frameworks, this project will provide scholarly publishing stakeholders with a means to migrate from data harvesting approaches to sovereign ongoing data control with data exchange and aggregation enabled via community-governed data usage terms and Web 3.0 technologies. The OAEUBDT-IDS aims to ensure that exchanged personal and sensitive usage data is as open and transparent as possible yet as controlled as necessary to support trust, and ensure that OAEUBDT-IDS participation does not harm data creators or linked data subjects including readers, scholars, institutions, and libraries.

Proposal Submission Instructions

We look forward to learning about your organizations and experience! Proposals should not exceed 10 pages of content plus a cover sheet. Please feel free to link to web-based materials to help us learn about your team and IDS related work. At a minimum, proposals should address the points listed above under the Proposal Notes and Budget Notes. We recommend that proposals include the following sections to assist our review:

- Summary
- About the Team
- Project Description
- Project Budget
- IDS Maintenance and Onboarding Post-Project

Proposals should be sent as a single .pdf file via email to executivedirector@oabookusage.org

Proposals will be reviewed as they are received. Reviews will take into account IDS experience, cost, and project alignment with our [core principles](#) recognizing we aim to launch in line with the [Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure](#).

Questions about this RFP should be directed to executivedirector@oabookusage.org. Responses will be sent via email and appended to this [RFP Q&A Document](#).

Appendix

Example IDSA Resources to Leverage

- Design Principles for Data Spaces: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5244996>
- International Data Space (IDS) Reference Architecture Model 4.0 https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDS-RAM_4_0
- IDS Certification Explained: https://internationaldataspaces.org/wp-content/uploads/dlm_uploads/IDSA-Position-Paper-IDS-Certification-Explained.pdf
- IDS Metadata broker Specification: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5222318>
- IDS Clearing House Specification: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5222633>

Background Resources about Book Usage Data

- COUNTER Code of Practice: <https://www.projectcounter.org/about/>
 - Note: the MVP use case for the OAEBUDT-IDS technical pilot is the multi-platform exchange of COUNTER compliant title and chapter related usage data.
- COUNTER SUSHI API <https://cop5.projectcounter.org/en/5.1/08-sushi/index.html> describes the current industry standard API in JSON
- E-Book Bibliographic Metadata Requirements in the Sale, Publication, Discovery, Delivery, and Preservation Supply Chain: NISO Recommended Practice 29-2022, while not specific to usage like COUNTER, describes related eBook metadata standards for reference and interoperability <https://www.niso.org/publications/rp-29-2022-ebmd>

International Data Space (IDS) Technical Development and Pilot for Scholarly Communication Usage Data Exchange

Prepared by the OA Book Usage Data Trust (OAEBUDT) effort

Proposal Questions and Answers

The following section reflects questions received from potential project partners during the RFP process.

- ❖ “Ideally publishers should become part of the Dataspace. Is there a strategic way to do it? We would foresee working together with you on the operational strategy for this. In the proposal you note: Proposals should also note the procedure and costs associated with adding users during and after this project to the production IDS environment, recognizing that a second cohort and a scalable service launch are expected within twelve months.”

Governance and membership processes are under development (outside of the scope of this technical development and pilot project). Our version zero of the Rulebook for the OAEBUDT-IDS will require organizational membership for publishers and other data producers of OA book usage data, and recipients of usage data, to be members in good standing to actively exchange data through the IDS. Such membership will be required when the service launches in 2025, although it is not required during this proof of concept research phase of alpha and beta pilots.

The data space Coordinating Office does require a mechanism to suspend data transfers or accounts in cases of noncompliance with OAEBUDT-IDS terms, which may result in membership and/or data flow suspension. The technical pilot will inform these processes by providing the GUI and will help increase our project team and advisor’s understanding of how such changes can be managed through the OAEBUDT-IDS interface.

- ❖ The Dataspace is for all data exchange? sales reports, analytics and metadata?

Since the IDS concept is relatively unknown in the scholarly publishing sector, the minimal viable product of the OAEBUDT-IDS technical pilot is focused on the transfer of COUNTER specified data elements named in the proposal. Proposals are welcome to address how the scope of work and cost could be adjusted to accommodate future extensions of the IDS for additional data elements or use cases that surface during this project. Extensibility is highly desired. While parties are interested in understanding the cost and requirements of transferring other types of data, this proof of concept pilot is limited to the COUNTER compliant usage statistics use cases detailed in the RFP. If a proposing team has experience extending an IDS framework to support the exchange of additional types of data between data producers and recipients, that should be noted in the proposal.

- ❖ Does this sandbox need to showcase different layers of data? e.g. seeing usage based on author, not ISBN (so multiple sources of data, then associating)

We do not anticipate making reporting dashboards for end user presentation (e.g. author, librarian, press director views) as that will be the role of the OAEBUDT IDS Data Recipients. However, visibility of available data sources and their associated licenses is vital for the OAEBUDT-IDS Data Recipient's data engineers and developers. It is unclear how "showcasing different layers of data" would fit into the IDS model - as the working assumption is that all dashboard development will be managed directly by Data Recipients outside of the IDS exchange ecosystem, while the IDS provides centralized data pipeline connection management. Examples of potential OAEBUDT-IDS Data Recipient analytics services that could reduce risk by migrating

from in-house data harvesting and aggregation operations to data connectors enabled by OAEBUDT-IDS participation include both nonprofit and commercial solutions (see [A](#), [B](#), [C](#)).

IDS Data Recipients will want to understand the data sources they can access via the OAEBUDT-IDS to pull into their dashboard and analytics products. More information about "showcasing different layers of data" is needed and the ability to include such functionality in this project phase will depend on the cost. It is currently unknown whether such layer visibility will be a must-have or nice-to-have feature.

- ❖ Which side of the dataspace should have a UI, providers or consumers or both? and which is expected to communicate programmatically?

At this time, we expect that a UI will be required for three user-types to interact with the data space: 1) data providers, 2) data recipients, and 3) the IDS Coordinating Office (to manage accounts). Experienced project teams are welcome to propose additional or alternative approaches based on their experience.

- ❖ Do both parties get a UI? If building on the consumer side, does it make sense to have both Big Query and Looker Studio?

At this time, we expect that a UI will be required for three user-types to interact with the data space: 1) data providers, 2) data recipients, and 3) the IDS Coordinating Office (to manage accounts). The OAEBUDT-IDS itself is not expecting to produce analytics or reports - rather, it will facilitate scalable data access to the data recipients who provide such products and services to others. Data recipients may have a variety of ways they expect to receive the data - research will be necessary to understand these functional requirements. Time should be allocated to work with the OAEBUDT team to understand what are priority use cases in preparation for launch. Experienced project teams are welcome to propose approaches based on their experience. Please note the OAEBUDT-IDS will support the exchange of sensitive data from commercial and public entities across multiple continents. Open source code and the ability for the OAEBUDT-IDS to be interoperable and support multiple platforms and avoid platform lock-in is preferred.

- ❖ Does the new solution still have to rely on ingesting all the data in Google Big Query on the consumer side after fetching and aggregating? And also lookerstudio?

Unlike the prior work done to develop the OAEBU workflows for the Academic Observatory, the OAEBUDT-IDS aims to create a neutral data intermediary capable of being certified as such within Europe. While the Academic Observatory effort illuminates the data dictionary and types of data being exchanged, its approach and code do not have to be copied or implemented in this project. Rather, the technical team should note how the proposed OAEBUDT-IDS approach limits risk by adopting a zero trust, zero-copy, digital twin, or other solution to minimize risks associated with multiple copies of sensitive data. The IDS-RAM should be a guide so that the OAEBUDT-IDS is capable of being certified through the IDSA.

- ❖ How cloud agnostic do you want to go? Get rid of Big Query and swap out for others (potentially open source and with no vendor lock-in)

Project teams are welcome to propose approaches based on their experience. Please note the OAEBUDT-IDS will support the exchange of sensitive data from commercial and public entities across multiple continents. Open source code and the ability for the OAEBUDT-IDS to be interoperable and support multiple platforms and avoid platform lock-in is preferred.

- ❖ All the aggregation from different data sources should be happening on the consumer participant end, correct?

This is an area that will require research and guidance from the technical team. Commercial partners cannot share their raw data directly with each other; yet, stakeholders seek trusted, transparent access to both aggregate numbers (sum counts calculated across all standard-compliant data feeds) and benchmark numbers (average calculated across all standard-compliant data feeds). Proposals should include time for research to work with pilot partners and the Technical Advisory Committee to explore and select ways for the stakeholders to generate and access such IDS-wide values calculated across participating IDS data providers, without exposing sensitive raw data feeds to all IDS participants. It is perhaps worth noting that in prior conversations, Plaid (FinTech) has come up as a potential industry effort to learn from, with aggregated asset and investment focused APIs providing a comparable use case where sensitive data is pulled from multiple secure data provider sources by the data recipient (<https://plaid.com/docs/>)

- ❖ Which party is responsible for cloud infrastructure during the development phase? Any cloud provider?

Proposals are welcome to suggest infrastructure providers based on their experience with other data spaces operating in Europe while supporting global supply chains and data flows. During this project, the proposing firm will manage such services on behalf of OPERAS, the OAEBUDT-IDS pilot partners, and OAEBUDT Coordinating Office. Costs to do this should be reflected in the proposal budget. It is important for the infrastructure to be developed to prevent lock-in and facilitate a future transition to a European, if not globally distributed, technical team. Open source solutions are highly preferred, but no specific cloud infrastructure or provider is required at this time.

- ❖ Do the core services (eg: DAPS or MIW, IDS Clearing House, IDS Metadata broker) have to be cloud agnostic?

Project teams are welcome to propose approaches based on their experience. Please note the OAEBUDT-IDS will support the exchange of sensitive data from commercial and public entities across multiple continents. Open source code and the ability for the OAEBUDT-IDS to be interoperable and support multiple platforms and avoid platform lock-in is preferred.

- ❖ Expectations from a technical standpoint? What is the level of architectural technical detail being asked here?

Given the global nature of the OAEBUDT-IDS, technical standards and standards federations should be leveraged as much as possible. For the technical architecture diagrams, industry standard approaches should be used. The level of detail should make it transparent to IDS participants how the data is flowing and what vendors and standards are being used. The project team will have to communicate the OAEBUDT-IDS technical architecture both to a general audience (e.g. in a single slide at conferences, to make clear what the systems approach is), and to a technical audience through the OAEBUDT-IDS rulebook (e.g. CTOs at participating companies, universities, libraries and other organizations.) Proposals are welcome to suggest approaches based on experience.

- ❖ What, if any, functional requirements have stakeholders specified to date?

In the context of exploring IDS participation terms in a 2023 “Rulebook Workshop”, 14 OA book usage infrastructure and publishing experts were given common information through a [working paper](#), prior to being surveyed about about the requirements and relative priorities of IDS policies and functionality related to usage data consistency, processing, transparency, security and risk

management. [Survey results](#) directly informed the priorities for this technical pilot. The [workshop proceedings](#) and resulting [Participant Rulebook](#) are also available for review.

❖ What is the proposal submission deadline?

Proposals are being accepted in a rolling fashion; however, to be fully considered we encourage proposal submission during May 2024.

❖ How will proposals be evaluated?

While there is not a scorecard for proposals, we expect proposal review discussions among our Technical Advisory Committee and Board of Trustees will focus on how well the proposal responds to the elements listed in the RFP, how well the proposed approach aligns with our stage of development and community, project cost and the approach to long term sustainability.

❖ Are you looking for a centralized or decentralized solution?

This is an area we look forward to exploring with our IDS partner. We know we want something that is certifiable by the IDSA, that meets emerging requirements including the dataspace protocol, and that is cost effective as a managed service for our Belgian-based IDS Coordinating Office to coordinate on behalf of a global set of commercial, public, and not-for-profit data providers and data recipients.

❖ Are you looking for help developing governance mechanisms for the IDS?

A separate ongoing project is developing governance building blocks for our IDS. We are not looking for this expertise at this time. Note: this project recently published [version 0 of our participant rulebook](#).

❖ Who is the project going to be contracted through?

[OPERAS](#) will act as the fiscal sponsor for this work, as it is the fiscal sponsor of the OA Book Usage Data Trust's Coordinating Office. OPERAS is a not-for-profit Belgian organization in the process of becoming an European Research Infrastructure Consortium via the [OPERAS-PLUS](#) project.

❖ Which IDS services are required as the proposal describes both a minimum viable product and a need for an extensible data space model?

While the Minimum Viable Product for the alpha cohort of pilot organizations is restricted to five data exchange use cases described on pg. 18 of the [OA Book Usage Data Trust Participant Rulebook](#), the proposed solution should be extensible to other scholarship usage and impact related data exchanges as described in Parts I and II of the rulebook. As described in the RFP, a technical roadmap deliverable would identify additional development phases that can build upon the foundational work completed in this project. Extensibility and scalability of the OAEBU data model created in this project is necessary. Proposals are encouraged to address how functional requirements related to extensibility will be documented and ultimately addressed in the technical roadmap.

❖ What is your approximate budget for this work?

While a specific budget has not been defined, proposals are encouraged to consider a staged research and development approach that accomplishes the deliverables outlined in the RFP while minimizing the budget for this first "alpha" phase of IDS development. Additional research and development beyond this proposal is expected. The foundational model created must be extensible while also being able to be launched as a service. A methodology for capturing future potential requirements and documenting them in a technical roadmap should be described in the proposal.

❖ Will the selected partner have a role to play in fundraising?

Fundraising will occur once a technical partner is identified. Joint fundraising is welcomed for this project and/or future phases e.g. via European funding programmes or other opportunities. OPERAS has a long history of collaborating on such [projects](#) through Horizon Europe. Partners in other countries may also fundraise to explore extensibility and connections to the data space.

OA BOOK USAGE DATA TRUST

*Facilitating global
automated usage
data exchange that
is as open as possible
and as controlled
as necessary*

OUR HISTORY

Building upon 8+ years of research, our partner network is working to launch a certifiable, community-governed International Data Space (IDS) to serve the public and private organizations that communicate and understand the impacts of open access on book publishing

NEUTRAL NETWORK

As an IDS data intermediary, we aim to provide controlled usage data transit between usage data creators and the many innovators who rely on usage data to support reporting and decision-making, all while supporting trust, ethical use and increased data quality

HOW A DATA SPACE CAN AID USAGE METRICS OPERATIONS

**Replace data
harvesting with
rules-based
data exchange**

**Access usage
data feeds
direct from
partners**

**Facilitate
multiparty usage
data governance
and licensing**

**Improve usage &
impact data
quality and
interoperability**

OUR VISION & VALUES

Our network works towards a future where the community governed sharing of quality, interoperable open access (OA) book usage data is both sustainable and transparent. As community-governed open infrastructure, we commit to being responsive, ethical, collaborative, inclusive, and data exchange focused

OUR MISSION

We champion strategies for the improved publication and management of open access books by exchanging reliable usage data in a trusted, equitable, and community-governed way

Innovating together to
improve scholarship
impact analytics

JOIN US

Follow our announce-list and social media, and get involved through community consultations, focus groups, and board committees

www.oabookusage.org

zenodo.org/communities/oaebu

@OAEBU_Project

OA BOOK USAGE DATA SPACE PILOT

2024-2025

A small group of monograph usage data creators and recipients are invited to join the OA Book Usage Data Trust to:

- Collaborate with data space experts to prepare and connect usage data feeds to the first scholarly communications data space (IDS) to transit usage at levels of openness that align with existing licensing agreements

- Participate in an ROI study to understand the financial benefits of IDS participation

- Inform the data model and technical and data governance processes for the data space through governance committees

Priority API use-cases for the pilot to enable include:

- Multi-platform usage data exchange and receipt
- COUNTER-compliant usage data aggregation for titles and chapters disciplinary benchmarking

BENEFITS TO PILOT PARTNERS

Recognition as a book industry leader supporting the shift to sovereign data exchange

Opportunity to understand your own organizational staff and resource savings (ROI) to justify future data space participation

Opportunity to inform the data space technical roadmap

Seat at the table developing the first certifiable data space for scholarly communications usage and impact data

Explore how to reduce legal risk through machine-mediated, rules-based data sharing

Explore the controlled, auditable exchange of sensitive usage data to customers and partners according to contractual terms

To support staffing, and sustainability modeling, pilot partners are asked to financially contribute the equivalent of \$10,000-\$15,000USD towards onboarding and data modeling consultation

TENTATIVE PILOT SCHEDULE

Q1 2024 to Q2 2024	Pilot partners commit to participation; cohorts form Inform OA book usage specific IDS data modeling; Review & process pilot participation agreements with internal legal & compliance teams; Join Technical Advisory Council
Q3 2024 to Q1 2025	Pilot partners engage consultants to understand baseline for ROI study; Prepare data & connect to IDS for data exchange
Q2 2025	Inform process revisions while working with consultants to understand ROI; Decide whether to continue in formal launch